

A review of the mental health, general well being and parenting styles of adolescents

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Abstract—Family plays a crucial role in a child's upbringing, influencing their development and support for emotions as well as their attachment preferences. Parenting styles play a significant part in family life since parents are important figures of attachment whose impact extends well beyond infancy, young adulthood and into adulthood. The primary source of the children's behavioural issues is believed to be the parents' nurturing and parenting practices. Parenting styles are characterized by a parent's general demeanour towards their offspring, encompassing methods and behaviours that influence a child's overall growth. The heightened levels of anxiety and psychological stress in the house are influenced by the parenting style, which in turn affects parent-child relationships as the base of one's childhood. Parents shape a child's attitude towards personal achievement, teach how to approach difficulties in life and satisfy psychological and physiological needs. A parenting style is understood as a set of approaches and behaviors a parent elicits towards a child. Children's psychological condition is influenced by their parents' interactions with them. The seed of good mental health is planted as early as childhood. Parents happen to be the most powerful catalysts in promoting good mental health in their children's lives. Parents' upbringing and child rearing styles are the important factors in changing and stabilizing the behavioral problems of children, similarly foundation of self-esteem is laid early in life. The transitional stage of adolescence is marked by a range of behavioural challenges, development, biology, socialization, and academics. It is feasible for emotional issues to surface later in life as an adult if mental health concerns are not addressed during adolescence. The style of parenting is one of the main determinants of development during this transitional time of life. Therefore present paper reviews the relationship between parenting style and adolescent's mental health and well being that how various forms of parenting approaches or styles (i.e., authoritarian, authoritative, permissive and uninvolved) affect the children's mental health and well being.

Keywords: Mental health, well being, adolescents, Parenting style, child rearing practice

I. INTRODUCTION

A stalled development process is often the cause of teenagers experiencing a variety of mental health problems and psychological crises and fast mental and physical growth occurs during adolescence (Baumrind, 1991). Poor mental health is the main factor contributing to impairment in youth, which has long-term effects and contributes significantly to the worldwide disease burden experienced by adolescents. Furthermore, risk-taking behaviours (such as self-harm, drug, alcohol, and tobacco use), hazardous sexual behaviour, and exposure to violence are all influenced by inadequate mental stateduring adolescence. Adolescents undergoing numerous transitions—physiological, psychological, intellectual, and social—as well as changes in family dynamics.. These changes may result in pressures that cause stress and lead to mental health issues. Furthermore, Kim-Cohen, Caspi, Moffitt, Harrington, Milne and Poulton (2003) stated that mental wellness problems are tend to occur first the latter stages of childhood and adolescence A child's or adolescent's family is a major socialization context that influences their health development. Children and adolescents' social, physical, and psychological development as well as their general health are significantly influenced by the everyday relationships with their families in which they acquire fundamental knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

Adolescence stage is known as the "explosion and strain" period. It is also a time of fast transformation and identity exploration. They are no longer regarded as either children or adults during this time. As they attempt to pursue both social group participation and parental independence, they become more aware of the realities of life (Santrock & Yussen, 1984). When a child enters the adolescent stage, he frequently experience psychological problems like physical stress, anxiety, anger, unfavourable complexes, and perhaps even sadness and dissatisfaction. Additionally the modern period is one of intense competition in both the workplace and in school. Competition is a necessary component, but it can also lead to disputes, conflicts, and anxiety. Mental health is a problem, increases particularly during adolescence, which is marked by highs and lows in the behavioural, psychological and emotional domain.

The onset of mental health illnesses is more likely to occur throughout the developmental stage of adolescence (Kessler et al., 2007). According to Kessler et al. (2007) and Kim-Cohen et al. (2003), failing to treat mental health problems that arise in childhood and adolescence, such as intellectual and developmental disabilities, can lead to the emergence of issues with mental health in adulthood. According to Kessler, Amminger, Aguilar, Alonso, Lee and Ustun (2007), mental health issues affect 10–20% of children and adolescents worldwide. Between 13 and 17 percent of teenagers globally experience emotional and behavioural issues (Barkmann and Schulte-Markwort, 2012). Proper diagnosis and treatment could avert mental health issues like depressive disorders, anxiety-related conditions, behavioural disorders, substance abuse disorders, hyperkinetic disorder, and suicide. Adolescence is a crucial time for fast mental as well as physical growth. Teenagers with psychological crises and various mental health conditions frequently arise as a consequence of a halted developmental process (Baumrind, 1991). The primary cause of disability among young individuals is inadequate mental state that has long-term effects and contributes significantly to the worldwide disease burden experienced by adolescents. Furthermore, risk-taking behaviours (such as self-harm, drug and alcohol abuse, and tobacco use), hazardous sexual behaviour, and exposure to violence are all influenced by poor mental health during adolescence. As stated by the World Health Organization (2020), these kinds of behaviours can have substantial long-term impacts. The onset of mental health illnesses is more likely to occur throughout the developmental stage of adolescence. Neglecting to take care of mental health concerns in youth and adolescence may cause mental health difficulties to arise later in life. The way in which kids view their parents' parenting has an impact on their mental well-being.

Adolescence is, as previously mentioned, a time of intense physical, cognitive, and psychosocial transformation that is challenging, stormy, and stressful. Nonetheless, positive psychology counselled us to recognize the positive features of adolescence health and functioning adequately rather than concentrating on the flaws and potential weaknesses. One important new area of research in child development is exploring issues of psychological wellness specifically as well as overall mental health. In recent years, research on children's psychological health has drawn more interest from around the world. Psychology and parenting practices have yielded a wealth of knowledge it matters how children are raised, anxiety and sadness are examples of internalizing (turned inward) mental health issues in children that arise from parenting, whereas aggression and other behavioural issues are examples of externalizing (turned outward) mental health issues. Additionally, depending on the sort of parenting, academic achievement is frequently altered, either beneficially or poorly.

World Health Organization (WHO, 2005) defines Children's and adolescents' mental health as the capacity to attain and sustain the highest possible level of psychological stability and well-being. It is closely associated with the extent of proficiency attained in social and psychological functioning. A good idea connected to one's societal, emotional, and psychological wellness is characterized as mental health. When someone is exhibiting a suitable degree of passion and behavioural adjustment, it is recognized as their psychological condition. According to WHO (2014), to be considered mentally healthy, a person must be able to fulfill their true potential, manage everyday stressors, perform effectively and efficiently, and give back to their community. A person's mental health is a crucial aspect of their overall health as every aspect of our thinking process occurs in our minds, ideas are generated there, and our minds also issue various directives that direct our actions, behavioural patterns, and interpersonal interaction, as well as determine that how we function in both our personal and social lives (Bhargava & Raina, 2007). The social, psychological, and emotional wellness are all included in mental health. An individual's mental health has an impact on his thoughts, feelings, and behaviours while he manages life. The state of one's mind influences how one responds to stress, interacts with people, and makes decisions. The basis for an individual's well-being and efficient functioning is their positive feeling of mental health. There is more to mental wellness than just not having a mental disorder.

Well-being is characterized as a positive adjustment resulting from intellectual, cognitive abilities emotional, social and cultural progress during human development. Physical and mental well-being is correlated. Adolescents who practice adaptability, perseverance, and judgmental skills has greater capacity for achieve general well-being and set themselves up for positive mental health as adults. Numerous situations, relationships with others, cultural systems, and religious convictions all affect the psychological well-being of adolescents. General mental health is referred to as psychological wellness in several studies. A pattern of psychological well-being or positive mental health has been supplied in recent decades by ideal overall prosperity well-being, which is defined as a rise in positive modes and a decrease in negative modes (Vitterso, 2001). Research on mental health and general psychological well being of teenagers has been conducted recently. There is evidence to show that teens' psychological and behavioural issues are getting worse. Emotional and social well-being is seen as mental health. The state of good mental health is essential for the proper growth of adolescents. Researchers have determined several aspects of teenage positive mental health. The two most emphasized dimensions are fortitude and intelligence of emotion. Resilient adolescents can handle the rigors of adulthood with ease.

The many approaches that parents typically take when raising their children are categorized under parenting styles. The actions, attitudes, and emotional climate of parents that raise their children are all included in these styles. A parent's set of attitudes towards their child that they impart to them so as to create a positive environment that includes guardian-child exchanges is known as parenting style. Different activities and socialization goals characterize parenting conduct, which is not exactly the same as parenting style. A parenting style's conceptualization requires a balance between authority and tenderness from parents. Adolescents' achievement motivation appears to be influenced by a variety of family characteristics, such as the educational attainment of parents, expectation from parents, and support from parents. Research has suggested that a number of characteristics play a crucial role in predicting the achievement motivation of adolescents. The constellation of attitudes towards the kid that are communicated to them and that, when combined, create a psychological atmosphere in which the parents' behaviours are exhibited is known as parenting style (Darling and Steinberg, 1993).

One method to consider a parenting style is as an emotional structure composed of common techniques parents use to raise their kids. Parents build their own parenting philosophies based on array of elements that change as their kids grow into adults and start to take on distinct personalities at different age stages. The relationship between parents and their newborn are the main features of infancy. The bond between them is more attachment-based. The adolescent years are thought to be a challenging developmental stage for both parents and children. Adolescence is a crucial time to grasp the relevance of continuing to provide excellent parenting. Adolescent parenting has an ongoing impact on behaviours that persist into adulthood.

Each parent approaches interacting with and guiding their children differently. This connection typically establishes a child's morals, values, and behaviour. Numerous factors impact the mental health and psychological well-being of teenagers. Adolescence mental health is thought to be primarily impacted by two distinct sorts of elements: personal (such as physiological and mental features) and environmental (such as home, educational institution, and peer age group) (Carr, 2015). Parenting style, or the family factor, has shown itself to be among the most significant elements influencing the mental health of adolescents (Newman et al., 2008). Adolescent personality development and other psychological traits are directly impacted by parenting style. Additionally, it has been shown to have a persistent impact on teenagers' mental health. (Rohner and Britner, 2002; Rohner et al., 2005; Huang et al., 2010). There are various parenting philosophies exist, and based on the situation, it's appropriate to employ multiple philosophies. Parenting style is greatly influenced by the way children are raised and deeply held views. Parenting approaches can evolve as parents adapt to changing circumstances and engage with diverse viewpoints. To have greater aware and thoughtful of how parents raise their kids, it is essential to comprehend The upsides and downsides of any parenting approach.

II. EXAMINING VARIOUS APPROACHES TO PARENTING

Adolescent behaviour is shaped and moulded by parents to a great extent. Considered from this angle, Baumrind's work—specializing in parenting styles—is acknowledged by Coste (2015), a developmental and clinical psychologist. The methods used by different parenting philosophies in the way they bring up their children and have different impacts on their mental and physical wellbeing. Despite the fact that there are numerous other parenting philosophies, but four well-researched and widely accepted approaches, authoritative, permissive, authoritative, and uninvolved/neglecting provide a thorough description of parental behaviour and its effects on children.

III. AUTHORITARIAN PARENTING

Parents that adopt this technique typically communicate in a one-way manner, enforcing tight restrictions that the child must follow. Typically, the rules are not clarified, and there is little to no opportunity for the youngster to negotiate. Parents hold their kids to these expectations and demand that they behave perfectly (Martinez and Garcia, 2007). Parents that are authoritarians typically have higher demands and are less flexible. Moreover, they happen to be usually fewer nurtured. Children of authoritarian parents are invariably the well-behaved in the group because they know what happens when they misbehave. Additionally, they are usually less nurturing. Children of authoritarian parents typically exhibit the highest levels of discipline in the classroom because they understand the repercussions of disobeying. Additionally, they are more adept at adhering to the precise directions required to complete a task. Moreover, these types of parenting able to generate offspring who are more aggressive but also shy, socially awkward, and incapable of making their own decisions. The aggressive behaviour can persist because these children lack the necessary guidance to control their anger, and their low self-esteem contributes to their incapacity to make decisions. A child may grow up to rebel against those in positions of authority as a result of their parents' severe rules and punishments. Negative developmental effects, such as increased symptomatic discomfort, diminished self-worth, and the emergence of withdrawn strategies for coping, have been linked to authoritarian and

emotionally distant parenting approaches (Reitzle, Winkler Metzke, Steinhausen, Eltern und Kinder Reitzle M., Winkler Metzke C., Steinhausen H. Eltern und Kinder: Der Zürcher Kurzfragebogen zum Erziehungsverhalten, 2001).

IV. AUTHORITATIVE PARENTING

Adolescents are encouraged to view their authoritative parents as resources, and they have a higher propensity to establish and define the rules that govern the family. Kids raised considering this particular kind of parenting are expected to be self-reliant and confident (Darling, 1999). At first, the idea of an authoritarian parenting style was initially established by Baumrind. According to Baumrind (1966) asserts that parents in positions of authority give their kids advice in a logical and issue-focused way. With this type of parenting, parents are often more demanding, thus good communication and a healthy relationship between them is encouraged (Piko & Balazs, 2012). Hoskins (2014) makes the observation that parents that are authoritative are more responsive and demanding, showing greater support for disciplined conduct. Parents like this utilise authority, logic, and shaping to reinforce goals; they also promote verbal compromise and explain the rationale underlying regulations. Positive teenage outcomes are more frequently linked to this parenting approach. Thus, for the majority of families, it is determined to be the most advantageous and successful parenting approach. Putting in another context, a strong parenting approach promotes the wellbeing of adolescence. Although they must meet Baumrind's criteria, parents must also have a low passive acceptant score in order to be labelled as authoritative. Children raised by authoritative parents are capable of self-control, confidence, and responsibility. They have improved emotional well-being and social outcomes due to their increased ability to control their negative emotions (Masuad, Ahmad and Fakhr, 2019). These parents configure their own children that they can achieve things on their own and that they have the ability to become independent.

V. PERMISSIVE PARENTING

A parenting style known as permissive parenting is one that emphasizes a significant level of responsiveness and little commands and demands. Despite having few limitations, guidelines permissive parents are typically quite affectionate. These parents frequently give the impression of being friends rather than parents, and try not to expect too much from their kids' behaviour. Permissive parenting is among the first parenting theories that Baumrind (2013) defines. Tolerant parents, according to Baumrind, "are more sensitive instead of strict." They avoid conflict, allow much self-regulation, are nontraditional and forgiving, and do not demand mature behaviour." Research indicates that parents who are overly forgiving may experience a range of negative outcomes from their lax discipline. Children raised by permissive parents may lack self-control, have poor social skills, be demanding and self-absorbed, and feel insecure because there are no boundaries or clear guidelines in place. A permissive parenting atmosphere lacks boundaries, rules, and expectations yet is full of warmth and affection. Children see these parents more as friends than as authoritative ones. Barton and Hirsch (2015) found a correlation between permissive parenting and higher academic entitlement as well as a link between higher perceived stress and worse mental health conditions, with variations between both parents in a few instances.

VI. UNINVOLVED PARENTING

Based on her observations with preschool-aged children, psychologist Diana Baumrind distinguished three parenting philosophies in the 1960s: authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive, researchers then included absentee or uninvolved parenting. In addition to meeting their child's basic needs (clothing, food, and shelter), parents who engage in indifferent parenting—also referred to as neglectful parenting, which certainly carries more negative connotations—also fail to address their child's wants and needs. These parents do not provide their children with much guidance, discipline, or nurturing. Furthermore, children are frequently abandoned to raise themselves and make all of life's decisions on their own. Many people naturally have an emotional bond with their children. However, in the context of absentee parenting, this connection isn't natural or innate. The parent's ability to show their child as much love and care as possible is greatly restricted since they comprehend an attachment. To grow, children need love, care, and encouragement. It follows that the detrimental effects of detached parenting on a child are not surprising. While it is the fact that children of absentee parents do often grow up to be independent and capable of meeting their own requirements. One big disadvantage of detached parenting is that these children don't develop an emotional connection with their absentee parent. Early neglect and inadequate respect and affection might lead to emotional demand in different relationships or reduced self-worth. Future attachment formation may be challenging for youngsters whose parents are not involved if they do not receive love and emotional support from their carers. Children with absentee parents find it more difficult to learn acceptable behaviour and boundaries at school and in other social situations when there are no boundaries at all in the home. As a result, they are more prone to misbehave. (Hong and Park, 2012).

Raising children is a challenging task that is impacted by a variety of variables, such as the child's temperament, socioeconomic background, and heredity. A parent's style of parenting may have different effects on different kids. Parent has a big impact on child's growth and mental health. It's important to keep in mind that there isn't a single parenting approach that is effective for everyone, even if authoritative parenting typically produces the best results. A flexible and compassionate approach is necessary for the dynamic process of parenting. Making decisions that support child's development into a happy, healthy, and well-adjusted adult can be made easier if parents aware of various parenting styles. Therefore we may conclude that one of the most crucial factors in preserving excellent health is mental wellness. This paper has investigated the parenting methods that teenagers learn in their families. Because at this point this is the vital moment when an adolescent begins to explore their identity, it is imperative that parents realize the value of positive parenting techniques and refraining from being harsh with their kids. Children whose parents use effective parenting strategies demonstrate early learning capacities and less disruptive behaviour. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, excellent parenting has an early influence on children when used controllably and with effort. Parenting also affects the ability of a parent to purposefully guide their children's lives.

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